

AI Methods for MNP Research

A Roadmap for the Possible Applications
of
Artificial Intelligence
Methods in
Micro and Nano-Plastics Research

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Abbreviations

AF4	Asymmetric Flow Field-Flow Fractionation
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CCD	Charge-Coupled Device
CMOS	Complementary Metal-Oxide-Semiconductor
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
EM	Electron Microscopy
FTIR	Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy
k-NN	k-Nearest Neighbours
LOD	Limit of Detection
LOQ	Limit of Quantification
MCT	Mercury Cadmium Telluride
ML	Machine Learning
MNP	Micro and Nano Plastic
NLP	Natural Language Processing
NN	Neural Network
py-GC-MS	Pyrolysis–gas chromatography–mass spectrometry
QA	Quality Assurance
QC	Quality Control
RF	Random Forest
SEM	Scanning Electron Microscopy
SVM	Support Vector Machine
UV-vis	Ultraviolet–visible spectrophotometry
YOLO	You Only Look Once

Introduction

Micro- and nanoplastics (MNPs) have become a critical concern in environmental science and human health. They have been detected in virtually every ecosystem, from the peaks of Mount Everest to the depths of the Mariana Trench, and in diverse organisms, including humans. Their ubiquity raises serious questions about ecological impacts and long-term health risks. Reliable detection and characterisation of MNPs, however, remains highly challenging. Unlike conventional analytes, MNPs represent a vast diversity of polymer types, sizes, shapes, degradation states, and chemical additives (ISO/TR 21960:2020; ISO 24187:2023). To properly characterise them, multiple particle attributes must be assessed simultaneously, often requiring complex workflows involving **sample collection, preparation, and analysis**. Each stage introduces biases and uncertainties that complicate comparability across studies.

Why Artificial Intelligence?

Conventional methods for MNP detection and analysis are labour-intensive, prone to human bias, and limited in scalability. A single environmental sample may yield thousands of particles, generating very large imaging and spectral datasets that exceed the capacity of manual or semi-manual evaluation. This is where **artificial intelligence (AI)**, and particularly **machine learning (ML)**, becomes valuable.

AI refers broadly to computational approaches that automate tasks requiring decision-making, perception, or pattern recognition. ML, a subfield of AI, focuses on algorithms that learn patterns from data for predictions or classifications. Within ML, we typically distinguish between:

- **Supervised learning:** where labelled examples are used to train models for classification (e.g. distinguishing plastics from pollen) or regression (e.g. predicting particle size or concentration). Labels are given either by experts or obtained from experiments.
- **Unsupervised learning:** where algorithms detect hidden structures in data, such as clustering spectra into polymer types, without prior labels.
- **Reinforcement Learning:** where algorithms are trained to realise some task by being given rewards when their behaviour is beneficial to it.
- **Mixed approaches:** combinations of the above approaches are possible, with some names such as **semi-supervised** or **self-supervised** learning appearing frequently in the literature.

Recent advances in ML have demonstrated impressive success in automating **image classification, natural language processing (NLP), and signal processing**, making these methods highly relevant to the challenges of MNP research (Goodfellow *et al.*, 2016; Zhang *et al.*, 2023).

The diagram below shows some examples of how AI can help within the MNP detection and analysis pipeline. The arrows indicate that results from later stages can provide feedback for earlier ones that can be used by ML algorithms for optimising performance with minimal use of available resources.

Purpose of this Roadmap

This document provides a **roadmap for applying AI/ML to MNP research**. It has three main aims:

1. **Highlight the challenges** in each stage of the MNP workflow where AI could provide value.
2. **Review current applications** of AI/ML, with references to key literature and available tools.
3. **Suggest future opportunities** for integrating AI methods to make MNP research more efficient, reproducible, and scalable.

The goal is not to provide an exhaustive technical manual, but rather a structured guide for scientists in the MNP community who are interested in exploring how AI and ML can support their research. By bridging perspectives from environmental science, analytical chemistry, and data science, aiming to stimulate collaboration and accelerate innovation in this field.

Sample Collection

Researchers are usually concerned in measuring several features of MNPs such as their distribution in the environment and level of toxicity. These involve collecting samples from water, soil or even biological tissue to detect, measure the amount, classify and analyse the effect of these particles. Obtaining such a sample is what we will call **sample collection**. The different kinds of materials in which MNPs can be present are usually called **matrices**. Each different matrix in each different location requires a different method of collection.

For sample collection, lots of tasks can be automated by AI. Collecting samples from the environment is a task that can be improved by robots due to several issues – the location can be of difficult access, can be hazardous or dangerous to humans or the sample can be too delicate for human manipulation. For robots to perform this task appropriately, they need to adapt to different situations, which means that decision-making algorithms should be used. These decision-making algorithms can be designed in such a way that robots are trained by examples or can classify situations in order to take certain kinds of decisions adaptively.

For instance, image processing algorithms can be used to identify the most appropriate areas to collect samples for instance, estimating areas with higher probability of certain kinds of MNPs. Self-driving algorithms can help robots to navigate with minimal human interference, avoiding hazards and respecting wildlife. Other recognition systems, such as sound, temperature, pressure and so on can also be used to help robots in such decisions. Robot arms can also be trained to collect samples from biological tissues with high precision and minimal damage.

Another possible contribution of AI is in using information processing techniques to redesign strategies for sample collection, optimising measures such as sample amount or sample type by deciding which are the best locations or methods to collect them.

Key Challenges

Most of the challenges in sample collection fall into one of the following categories:

- **Accessibility & safety of sampling sites:** many aquatic and terrestrial locations are remote, hazardous, or delicate, making manual collection costly or risky. Deep-sea trawling, polar expeditions, and polluted urban sites all pose logistical barriers (Sharma *et al.*, 2024; Zheng *et al.*, 2024).
- **Heterogeneity of environmental matrices:** the distribution of MNPs varies sharply with water depth, sediment grain size, flow regime, and biofilm presence, so representative sampling requires adaptive strategies. Conventional methods of obtaining samples often miss this variability (Bäuerlein *et al.*, 2023).
- **Sample integrity:** delicate MNP particles may fragment during manual collection (nets, pumps, cores), biasing size distributions. Cross-sample contamination from tools and airborne fallout is also common (Nayebi *et al.*, 2023).
- **Throughput and comparability:** large-scale surveys (rivers, coastlines, wastewater) demand many replicates. Manual workflows are slow, and inconsistent reporting hinders meta-analysis (ISO/TR 21960:2020; ISO 24187:2023).

- **Environmental disturbance:** over-sampling or invasive methods may damage ecosystems, disturb sediments, or bias biota uptake studies. Balancing coverage with minimal impact remains a challenge.

Current AI/ML Use

The usefulness of AI/ML methods has already been recognised in the field and applications of the technology have already been attempted. Some examples are listed below:

- **Autonomous navigation & remote platforms:** drones and autonomous underwater vehicles (AUVs) equipped with cameras and sensors use AI navigation to reach hazardous or remote areas with minimal human intervention. Self-driving algorithms then reduce operators' workloads and help to increase safety (Jin *et al.*, 2024).
- **Image-based hotspot detection:** AI-driven image recognition of water surfaces, aerial images, or sediment scans identifies areas of higher MNP accumulation (e.g. floating debris slicks, estuary convergence zones) are being used to guide targeted sampling. Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) have been trained for marine litter detection and adapted for MNPs (Wang *et al.*, 2023; Akkajit *et al.*, 2024).
- **Adaptive sampling robotics:** robotic arms and manipulators, guided by computer vision and ML-based decision-making, can collect tissue or sediment samples with high precision, reducing damage and variability. Early prototypes exist in biomedical and ecological monitoring (Rahimi *et al.* 2004; Zhang *et al.*, 2021), but applications to MNPs are still emerging (Pasquier *et al.*, 2022).
- **Environmental monitoring integration:** ML algorithms fuse satellite, drone, and in situ sensor data (temperature, salinity, turbidity, fluorescence) to predict MNP-rich zones, improving representativeness of collected samples (Han *et al.*, 2023).

Roadmap: Where to Go Next with AI/ML

There are several unexplored uses of AI/ML which can be further implemented for sample collection in the area. Some of these, which seem to be missing in the literature, are suggested below.

- **Smart survey design:** use of techniques such as **reinforcement learning** or **Bayesian optimisation** to dynamically decide where and when to sample based on real-time sensor inputs and historical data can help maximise representativeness while minimising costs. This is already done in several contexts (Greenhill *et al.*, 2020).
- **AI-assisted robotics for fragile matrices:** development of robotic samplers with force-feedback and vision-guided manipulation to minimise fragmentation of MNPs and cross-sample contamination is a possibility. Models can be trained with a range of supervised learning algorithms on “safe vs damaging” manipulations to guide operators or to completely automate the task (Billard & Kragic, 2019).
- **Automated contamination control during collection:** integrating onboard particle counters or fluorescence sensors into drones/ROVs to provide immediate contamination checks and flag anomalous samples can save time and improve the quality of samples. There are several

methods that can be used for detection of outlier as, for instance, **isolation forests** (Liu *et al.*, 2008).

- **Cross-scale integration:** combine remote-sensing (satellite/drone), local imaging, and physical sampling into a unified pipeline, where ML algorithms can be used to recommend when to escalate from cheap/large-scale observations to costly sample collection. This would require the combination of several technologies involving image processing and optimisation.
- **Adaptive, closed-loop sampling:** an endgame application could be obtained by coupling AI decision-making to robotics in autonomous vehicles, so that sampling tasks iteratively refine themselves in the field using reinforcement learning algorithms with minimal human interference.

Sample Preparation

After samples of a certain matrix containing MNPs are collected from the environment, they need to be properly prepared in order to be fed to different kinds of instruments that will take the appropriate measurements. We call this stage **sample preparation**. Effective preparation is hampered by a multiple of interrelated issues that introduce bias, limit comparability, and complicate downstream detection. In the following subsections, we summarise the main challenges in this stage, how AI is being currently used to assist and possible future uses of it in the area that might be worth exploring.

Key Challenges

The following (non-exhaustive) list summarises some of the main challenges related to the preparation of matrix samples containing MNPs for analysis by different methods:

- **Matrix Heterogeneity & Representativeness:** environmental matrices (water, sediments, biota) differ in organic load, salinity, turbidity, mineral content, and co-particles (e.g. fibres, cellulose). Subsampling and fractionation often introduce bias in both recovery and polymer composition (Sharma et al., 2024; Bäuerlein et al., 2023).
- **Weathering, Sorbed Species & Biofilms:** environmental ageing through oxidation, UV, hydrolysis or mechanical abrasion modifies chemical, surface, and physical properties of MNPs (Pfohl et al., 2022; McGivney et al., 2020). These changes complicate isolation and identification, imposing constraints on upstream protocol design. Specific effects include:
 - **Altered spectral signatures:** new functional groups and adsorbed organics or metals shift IR/Raman peaks, overlap bands, or suppress signals (Vasudeva et al., 2024; McGivney et al., 2020).
 - **Density modifications & aggregation:** adsorption of biofilm/organic matter/metals increases mass, changes buoyancy, and disrupts float/sink separations (Jian et al., 2022; Jiang et al., 2023).
 - **Increased heterogeneity:** a polymer type may diverge into multiple weathering states, each with distinct spectral/density profiles (Pfohl et al., 2022).
 - **Biofilm formation & sorption interactions:** microbial colonisation alters surface roughness/hydrophobicity, enhancing binding of metals/organic pollutants; biofilms may fluoresce or absorb analytes, interfering with Raman/fluorescence measurements (Moyal et al., 2023; Jiang et al., 2023).
 - **Downstream consequences:** Choices in reagents, storage, drying, or handling can strip sorbed materials or further oxidise surfaces, reducing comparability across studies (Pfohl et al., 2022).
- **Contamination:** one of the most pervasive challenges in preparation. It can happen across all handling steps, leading to over- or underestimation of environmental loads (Zheng et al., 2024; Nene et al., 2025; Nayebi et al., 2023). Mitigating it requires blanks, surrogate spikes, and context-aware QA/QC (Munno et al., 2023). Common contamination pathways include:
 - **Airborne fallout:** fibres or fragments settle onto open vessels or filters; synthetic fibres are especially mobile and hard to distinguish (Nayebi et al., 2023).
 - **Cross-sample carryover & equipment wear:** tools, nets, tubing, and filters may shed or hold particles, transferring them between samples (Nene et al., 2025; Nayebi et al., 2023).

- **Reagent & solution contamination:** digestants (e.g. H₂O₂, KOH), density solutions (NaBr, ZnCl₂), or dyes may carry microplastic fragments unless pre-filtered (Nene et al., 2025).
- **Sample loss, breakage & recovery efficiency:** mechanical stresses (sonication, vacuum filtration) can fragment particles; adhesion to surfaces or clogging causes variable recoveries (30–95 %) across studies (Zheng et al., 2024; Nene et al., 2025).
- **Preservation, storage & pre-treatment effects:** during storage/transport, particles may aggregate, swell, shrink, or transform in response to temperature, pH, or preservatives (e.g. ethanol, formalin), altering size, shape, or mass metrics relevant for ML classification (Nayebi et al., 2023).
- **Pollen Interference:** pollen acts as a matrix interference (not a plastic contaminant), but its presence in extracts severely confounds identification. Key issues include:
 - **Morphological overlap & misclassification:** under light microscopy, pollen (10–100 μm) can mimic irregular plastic fragments, leading to >50 % misidentification in some workflows (Grazl et al., 2024).
 - **Spectral interference in vibrational methods:** cellulose/sporopollenin in pollen walls produce IR/Raman bands overlapping polymer fingerprints; absence of biogenic spectra in reference libraries worsens false positives.
 - **Incomplete removal by chemical/enzymatic digestion:** oxidative reagents (e.g. 30 % H₂O₂, Fenton's) may not fully degrade pollen walls and may damage sensitive polymers at >60 °C; enzymatic treatments (cellulase, protease) are selective but expensive/time-consuming and lack standard protocols.
 - **Size-based pre-filtration trade-offs:** coarse filters (20–50 μm) may exclude pollen but risk losing small MNPs; there is no consensus on optimal pore sizes or filter materials.
 - **Emerging fluorescence discrimination:** multi-channel fluorescence (excitation–emission mapping) shows promise in differentiating plastics from pollen taxa, but specialized instrumentation is rare in routine MNP labs.
- **Lack of Standard Methods & Harmonised Reporting:** community-adopted, uniform protocols for prep (reagent concentrations, filtration media, separation steps, instrument settings) and metadata reporting are essential for inter-lab comparability. Standardisation for microplastics (1 μm–5 mm) is emerging, but for nanoplastics it remains nearly absent (Nene et al., 2025; Nayebi et al., 2023). Furthermore, the absence of harmonised reporting of prep metrics (spikes, recoveries, blanks, LOD/LOQ) hinders meta-analysis and model transfer (Cowger et al., 2020; Munno et al., 2023).
- **Processing Efficiency and Methodological Trade-offs:** even with well-controlled contamination and matrix variability, the technical design of preparation steps itself introduces biases. Decisions on sieving, digestion chemistry, and workflow automation determine both throughput and data fidelity.
 - **Size-Fractionation & Recovery Bias:** complex multi-step sieving, filtration, density separation, and ultrafiltration (e.g. AF4) involve tradeoffs between throughput and losses. Nanoplastics are especially susceptible to being lost or miscounted during transitions (Prume *et al.*, 2023)
 - **Chemical Digestion & Polymer Damage:** biogenic matter removal (using H₂O₂, KOH, enzymes) carries risk of mass loss or alteration of polymer surfaces; the optimal digestion recipe depends heavily on matrix and polymer type (Prata *et al.*, 2024; Thomas *et al.*, 2020).

- **Throughput vs. Fidelity:** manual workflows (rinsing, transfers, filter handling) are slow and introduce variance; when scaling up, errors escalate unless QA/QC and automation mitigate them (Cowger *et al.*, 2020b; Thomas *et al.*, 2020).

While not purely sample preparation issues, two further obstacles complicate particularly nanoplastic detection by Raman spectroscopy and thus feed back into sample preparation demands (Fang *et al.*, 2024):

- **Spatial Resolution Limitations:** conventional confocal Raman microscopy is diffraction-limited, with laser spot sizes larger than most nanoplastics (1 nm–1 µm). This leads to weak or averaged signals and loss of particle-specific information (Fang *et al.*, 2024).
- **Salt Interference in Seawater Samples:** during drying of marine samples, crystallization of salts (e.g. NaCl, MgCl₂, CaSO₄) on the substrate produces strong Raman bands and heterogeneous surfaces that obscure the already weak nanoplastic signals and increase background fluorescence (Beres *et al.*, 2024; Caldwell *et al.*, 2024).

Current AI/ML Use

The literature on the use of ML techniques for sample preparation is remarkably sparse: nearly all published ML works remain in downstream analysis, with virtually none addressing contamination control or interference mitigation during sample preparation. This represents a clear opportunity for developing targeted ML workflows to flag or prevent pollen and plastic cross-contamination before samples ever reach the spectrometer or microscope.

One notable development is the use of multi-modal sensing combined with ML for particle classification. For example, Beres *et al.* (2024) demonstrated an *in situ* aerosol sensor that merges holographic imaging and fluorescence measurements with ML to classify airborne microparticles. In their results, common microplastic polymers (1–1000 µm) exhibited measurable fluorescence signatures that allowed them to be distinguished from naturally fluorescing particles like pollen with high accuracy. By feeding both the holographic shape data and multi-wavelength fluorescence data into a machine learning model, they achieved over 90% classification accuracy in separating five polymer types of microplastics from several pollen taxa and mineral dust.

Roadmap

Since sample preparation is a manual, labour-intensive process, machine learning alone – at least without specialized instrumentation – cannot directly prevent contaminants from entering samples. However, by labelling each batch as “clean” or “not clean,” researchers can train an ML model to flag samples that are contaminated or contain excessive pollen.

- **Contamination:** record simple spectroscopic (e.g. UV-Vis) or turbidity scans of each new batch of digestion/separation reagents and train a small random-forest or SVM model to recognize the signature of “clean” vs. “contaminated” lots. Any lot that falls outside the learned envelope is quarantined and pre-filtered.
- **Pollen Interference Mitigation & Early Flagging**
 - **Microscopy-image classification:** build a training set of pollen vs. plastic fragments under your specific prep conditions (e.g. mounting medium, illumination). A U-Net or

ResNet classifier can then run *before* any further extraction: every object on a filter is flagged as “likely pollen” vs. “likely plastic,” allowing you to quantify and, if needed, remove pollen-rich filters or apply extra digestion steps.

- **Multi-spectral fluorescence classification:** pollen and plastics often have distinct fluorescence excitation-emission landscapes. Train a small neural network on 2D excitation-emission matrices to automatically tag each particle. If > X % of particles look “pollen-like,” you’re prompted to adjust your chemical or enzymatic digest protocol.
- **Reinforcement-learning for pre-filtration:** frame the choice of pre-filter pore size and material as a sequential decision problem: an RL agent “recommends” the next pore size based on the current sample’s turbidity, pollen count estimate, and historic recovery rates – optimizing the trade-off between pollen exclusion and microplastic retention.
- **Smart Robotic Arms and Automated Manipulation:**
 - **Precision and reproducibility:** robotic manipulators, guided by ML-based computer vision, can handle delicate filtration and transfer steps (e.g., moving filters between digestion and rinsing) with micrometre accuracy, reducing particle loss and cross-contamination.
 - **Adaptive force control:** reinforcement learning algorithms can optimise grip and motion parameters by feedback from pressure or torque sensors, ensuring gentle manipulation of fragile filters and membranes.
 - **Integrated contamination control:** robotic systems could incorporate real-time particle counters or cameras to monitor airborne and contact contamination, pausing workflows or replacing consumables automatically when anomalies are detected.
- **Optimal Preparation Through Feedback and Process Modelling**
 - **Closed-loop optimisation:** AI models can monitor intermediate indicators, such as turbidity, fluorescence, pH, or conductivity, to dynamically adjust digestion parameters (temperature, oxidant concentration, reaction time). For instance, Bayesian optimisation or reinforcement learning can seek optimal trade-offs between digestion efficiency and polymer preservation.
 - **Real-time prediction of recovery and degradation:** ML models trained on spike-recovery datasets can predict the probability of polymer damage or incomplete digestion under specific conditions, advising operators before processing valuable samples.
 - **Sensor fusion and digital twins:** multi-sensor data streams (temperature, pH, reagent conductivity, optical density) can feed digital-twin simulations of the digestion workflow, allowing parameter testing without consuming samples. This approach mirrors recent developments in smart manufacturing and bioprocess control.
- **Quality Control and Contamination Detection through ML Classification**
 - **Reagent and blank assessment:** simple UV-Vis, FTIR, or fluorescence scans of reagent batches and procedural blanks can be used to train classification models (e.g., random forests or SVMs) to distinguish “clean” vs “contaminated” materials. Anomaly detection methods (e.g., one-class SVMs, autoencoders) can flag suspect batches before use.
 - **Pollen and matrix interference detection:** CNNs and U-Nets trained on microscopic images can automatically label objects as pollen, plastic fragment, or mineral,

allowing early correction of contaminated preparations. Multi-spectral fluorescence maps can provide complementary classification cues.

- **Automated logging and traceability:** each step of sample preparation could be monitored and logged automatically by an AI-based quality-assurance system. Deviations from standard conditions (e.g., excessive fluorescence in blanks, unusual temperature profiles) would trigger alerts, ensuring data traceability consistent with ISO 24187 validation guidelines.

Sample Analysis

Although MNP pollution has emerged as a global concern, with particles detected across diverse ecosystems and in human exposure pathways as we have already discussed in previous sections, reliable analysis remains a major bottleneck due to the heterogeneity of particle properties and the complexity of analytical workflows. Current methods require the detection of particles and measurement of their morphological attributes, as well as the chemical identification and characterization of polymer type, degradation state, additives, and contaminants. Techniques such as optical microscopy, μ (FT)IR, μ Raman spectroscopy, and mass spectrometry each provide valuable insights but are limited in scalability and comparability. Manual or semi-manual data evaluation is particularly time-consuming, prone to bias, and restricts throughput.

In the same way as for the other steps in the MNP research pipeline, AI (and particularly ML) offers promising avenues to address these challenges by automating particle detection, improving spectral classification, and enhancing reproducibility across studies. In the following sections we review the current state of ML approaches, highlight how AI can augment established analytical methods, and discuss emerging strategies for advanced ML applications. By synthesizing perspectives from analytical chemistry, environmental science, and data science, we identify key opportunities and challenges in applying AI to MNP sample analysis and outlines directions for future research.

At the sample analysis stage, researchers face enormous bottlenecks. A single environmental sample can yield tens or hundreds of thousands of particles, generating very large datasets from spectroscopic, microscopic, or mass spectrometric measurements. Manual or semi-manual evaluation of such data is not only extremely labour-intensive and time-consuming, but also prone to operator bias and limits the comparability of results across studies.

Concerning the various properties that can be the target of analysis, we can broadly distinguish between two main tasks:

1. **Particle identification and measurement** of attributes such as total number, area, length, width, and colour.
2. **Chemical identification and characterisation** of detected microplastics, including polymer type, degradation state, additives (or their absence due to leaching), contaminants, and mass.

Some analytical devices can address both tasks simultaneously, for example, micro-spectroscopy instruments such as μ (FT)IR and μ Raman. Others are better suited for a single task: optical microscopy for particle identification, or mass spectrometry techniques such as py-GC-MS for polymer identification and mass. Importantly, no single instrument or methodology outperforms all others across every dimension of analysis. The choice of method should be guided by the specific scientific questions being asked, and by the balance between depth of characterization and throughput required.

Against this backdrop, AI/ML offer a way forward. By automating steps in data processing, particle detection, and polymer classification, AI can significantly reduce manual workload, increase throughput, and improve reproducibility of results.

Recent advances suggest that AI has the potential to handle the scale and complexity of modern microplastics datasets more efficiently than traditional library matching or manual interpretation approaches (Weisser *et al.*, 2022). In addition, AI methods can uncover subtle patterns in spectral or imaging data that might be overlooked with conventional analyses, opening new opportunities for understanding microplastic behaviour and impacts.

Our goal is to provide a structured overview of how AI/ML can support and advance the area by

- Summarising the current analytical challenges that motivate the adoption of AI.
- Reviewing the state of existing AI/ML methods in this field.
- Highlighting their potential contributions, limitations, and future research needs.

By bridging perspectives from analytical chemistry, environmental sciences, and data science, we seek to inform both domain experts and AI researchers, and to stimulate further collaboration across disciplines.

In the following sections, we first review the current analytical approaches to microplastics research, distinguishing between methods for particle detection and measurement, and those for chemical identification and characterization. Within each category, we highlight where AI/ML methods have already been applied and where clear opportunities remain. Finally, we discuss the broader challenges, limitations, and opportunities for AI in this field, before concluding with recommendations and perspectives on future directions for strategies combining multiple analytical techniques for moving toward more automated, integrated workflows.

Due to the several different kinds of analysis, we will separate this chapter in subchapters corresponding to each of the main ones.

Particle Identification and Measurement: number, size, shape, distribution, etc.

Optical Microscopy

Optical microscopy is one of the most widely used techniques for detecting and characterising MNPs. It fundamentally produces raw image data – digital micrographs or holograms – captured via high-resolution cameras, often CCD or CMOS sensors. These raw images record pixel-level information, including light intensity values, contrast, and colour distribution (Culley *et al.*, 2024). This raw output does not directly distinguish MNPs from other particles but forms the essential basis for further segmentation, feature extraction, and classification through manual or AI-assisted analysis.

Once analysed, the obtained information typically includes morphological features (shape, size, colour), classification into particle types (fibres, fragments, beads), and in some methods, quantitative estimates of number and mass concentration. Detection ranges vary by platform: conventional microscopy is effective above $\sim 100\mu\text{m}$, while more advanced approaches extend from $\sim 100\mu\text{m}$ to 5 mm (e.g., holographic systems such as CompNet) or 1–3mm in specialized spectroscopic holography systems (Jin *et al.*, 2024; Zhu *et al.*, 2024).

Additionally, optical microscopy is often combined with other techniques such as μ FTIR or Raman spectroscopy. In the case of single point measurements (i.e. MCT detector on a μ FTIR device), the later particle detection depends directly on how efficiently particles or features are detected on the optical image. Commercial software already provide tools or plug-ins allowing for automatic particle detection in images but is mainly based on a simple thresholding of the image (i.e. OPUS particle finder (μ FTIR), Witec Control particle scout (Raman)). This method has rather significant drawbacks, such as (1) the need of a perfectly smooth and clean background, (2) is hardly reproducible, (3) cannot handle variation of pixel colour intensity within a particle. Thus, algorithms for accurate and fast particle detection in optical microscopy images can greatly improve the general quality of the analysis.

Electron microscopy

Electron microscopy (EM) is also widely applied in MNP research. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) focuses a beam of electrons on a sample and different types of detectors will then collect different types of scattered electrons. The use of electrons instead of the use of light allows for significantly higher resolution compared to optical microscopy (Kalaronis *et al.*, 2022). SEM was previously applied to microplastic surface morphology characterization to contribute to the MNP identification in several studies (Sekudewicz *et al.*, 2021; Sunitha *et al.*, 2021; Rasta *et al.*, 2020). In addition to the MNP identification process, SEM is very useful to characterize the morphology of spiking material (Mitrano *et al.*, 2019) or investigate particle surface of weathered MNP (Ainali *et al.*, 2021) for example.

Current AI/ML Use

The main purpose of AI in MNP analysis is to improve accuracy, reproducibility, and scalability. Training AI models for identification tasks, which is usually done using supervised learning techniques, requires large annotated image datasets. Preferred datasets contain diverse particle types under both laboratory and natural imaging conditions, ensuring robustness against environmental variability (Zhang *et al.*, 2023). Balanced datasets that represent the full heterogeneity of MNPs are critical to avoid bias toward specific morphologies or backgrounds (Han *et al.*, 2023). Table 1 below provides an overview of established AI/ML approaches.

Table 1.: A comparison of different AI/ML approaches.

Model	Purpose	Advantages	Limitations	References
CNN	Object detection, image classification	High accuracy, learns spatial features directly	Requires large labelled datasets; computationally intensive	Wang <i>et al.</i> , 2023 Sukkuea <i>et al.</i> , 2025
Vision Transformer Based Models	Object Detection, Image Classification	High Accuracy, learns global features instead of local features.	Requires large dataset and computational resources.	Sukkuea <i>et al.</i> , 2025

Model	Purpose	Advantages	Limitations	References
U-Net / MP-Net	Image segmentation	Excellent for delineating particles from background, even in complex fluorescence images	Sensitive to training data variability; requires annotated masks	Park <i>et al.</i> , 2022
YOLO	Real-time object detection	Fast inference, suitable for deployment in field monitoring	May struggle with small or overlapping particles	Akkajit <i>et al.</i> , 2024
RF	Morphological classification	Robust against noise, interpretable feature importance	Performance depends on quality of hand-engineered features	Lorenzo-Navarro <i>et al.</i> , 2018 Thota <i>et al.</i> , 2024 Withana <i>et al.</i> , 2024
SVM	Shape/colour classification	Effective with limited training data; good for binary classification	Less efficient with large datasets or multi-class problems	Lorenzo-Navarro <i>et al.</i> , 2018
k-NN	Morphology-based classification	Simple, interpretable	Sensitive to irrelevant features; computationally expensive at scale	Lorenzo-Navarro <i>et al.</i> , 2018
Holographic Feature SVM	Image classification	Higher accuracy, works well with small datasets, simple, robust to morphological variation, computationally efficient as compared to CNNs, interpretable	High pre-processing complexity, sensitive to noise in phase reconstruction, unscalable to multi-classes	Bianco <i>et al.</i> , 2020
Decision Tree	Classification based on extracted features	Interpretable, quick to train, smaller datasets	Prone to overfitting, limited for high-dimensional data	Withana <i>et al.</i> , 2024

Despite progress, challenges remain. The primary hurdles include the need for extensive sample preparation, the performance drop of AI models in complex environmental settings, and the difficulty in creating large, diverse, and standardized image datasets for training. Furthermore, some methods are still limited in their ability to detect the smallest MPs or specific particle types (Mariano *et al.*, 2021).

AI combined with optical microscopy offers a pathway to standardized, automated, and large-scale microplastic monitoring. Integration of hybrid imaging approaches, building diverse datasets, and better preprocessing and background correction may improve the applicability and robustness of these models in complex environmental samples and food matrices.

Recently, some studies have applied segmentation models to optical images (Foetisch *et al.*, 2024) and to SEM micrographs (Stine *et al.*, 2023) to automatically recognise particles and assign them a class for their identification, making it possible to analyse a significantly higher number of particles at once and improving considerably user bias. Additionally, the commercial software Aztec[®] (Oxford Instruments, UK) can now be purchased with a feature using deep neural networks to detect particles in images.

Chemical Identification and Characterization: plastics, additives, contaminants and other chemicals or adsorbed species

Current AI/ML Use

In the domain of analytical chemistry, analysing measurement data is a common problem often referred to as chemometrics. Within chemometrics, the application of advanced data-analytical approaches such as ML has a long track record, dating back as far as the 1960's. Still, chemometric approaches are often neglected within the MNP literature, where we find a strong preference towards spectral library search.

Spectral library search (aka. database matching, spectral matching) performs a similarity search in a database of known spectral references, where the similarity criterion is most commonly the Pearson correlation coefficient. It is thus a special case of the k -Nearest Neighbours (k -NN) classifier for $k = 1$. Spectral libraries are available for purchase from most analytical instrument manufacturers, but there are also examples of public domain databases.

Weisser *et al.* (2022) reviewed 100 studies published between 2020 and 2021 using FTIR for MNP identification and showed that 62% used spectral library search, 10% used manual interpretation and 5% used ML (the last 23% represents non reported data).

On one hand, spectral library search has already been widely applied and, when the database is correctly built and tuned with suitable thresholds selected, very efficient. The tuning of the database and parameters requires expert knowledge though. Commercial databases sometimes lack transparency and adaptability, which can be a drawback of the approach, however, from a computational point of view, the analysis of large datasets can be extremely time consuming. On the other hand, ML requires expert knowledge in model building and spectroscopy. In addition, the inclusion of new reference spectra is more difficult than database matching. However, it can produce quick, accurate and robust results. Additionally, unsupervised ML (Hufnagl and Lohninger, 2020) can help identify groups of spectra which would be overlooked in target analysis.

With the publication of ISO 24187:2023¹ a system of the most widely used algorithms and basic means for validation has been defined. This ISO standard reunites spectral library search with ML, by categorizing it among the instance-based learners. Examples include (Brandt *et al.*, 2020; Kedzierski *et al.*, 2019; Liu *et al.*, 2019; Pimpke *et al.*, 2017, 2018, 2020; Renner *et al.*, 2017, 2019; Zhang *et al.*, 2018). Instance-based learners use data examples and a similarity criterion to infer the class of the unknown spectrum. This is very different from model-based learning, where the data is used to infer a statistical model that predicts the class of the unknown spectrum. This is also what is most commonly understood as “machine learning”. Examples for ML include (Da Silva *et al.*, 2020; Hahn *et al.*, 2019; Hufnagl *et al.*, 2019, 2022; Paul *et al.*, 2019; Serranti *et al.*, 2018; Shan *et al.*, 2019; Weisser *et al.*, 2021).

This new common systematic is relevant insofar as spectral library search is usually not validated by established approaches such as the confusion matrix method (Westad & Marini, 2015), whereby differences in performance would become quite evident. ISO 24187:2023 recommends the use of confusion matrices for algorithm validation and performance comparison and describes the steps to compute sensitivity, specificity and precision of an algorithm. However, the topic of validation is kept rather ambiguous in the newer ISO 16094-2.

Concerning the state-of-the-art of software for the purpose of MNP analysis, different options are currently available:

- **ImageJ** (<https://imagej.net/ij/>) is a well-established image analysis tool, which offers a broad set of algorithms for image analysis.
- **OpenSpecy** (<https://www.openanalysis.org/>) allows the analysis of both (FT)IR and Raman spectra based on an R package or via an online webtool (Cowger *et al.*, 2021). OpenSpecy provides spectral library search as well as an experimental deep-learning neural network for spectrum identification.
- **siMPle** (<https://simple-plastics.eu/>) is perhaps the most widely used freeware concerning the processing of μ FTIR imaging data (Pimpke *et al.*, 2020). It relies on a special algorithm that combines the raw results from spectral library search with lateral neighbourhood information of hyperspectral image pixels.
- **GEPARD** is tailored towards single-point analysis, for both μ Raman and μ FTIR. Spectra are identified by means of spectral library search, though particle locations might either be determined by means of watershed transform or a pre-trained convolutional neural network (Brandt *et al.*, 2020).
- The most widely used machine-learning-based commercial software for μ FTIR imaging is **Purency® Microplastics Finder**, which has been introduced to the market in 2021 (Hufnagl *et al.*, 2019 and 2022). Earlier versions of the machine learning approach have been applied by Frei *et al.* (2019), Schrank *et al.* (2022), Kernchen *et al.* (2022), Möller *et al.* (2022) and Teichert *et al.* (2021). The commercial version has also been applied by La Cecilia *et al.* (2023), Guo *et al.* (2024), Peng *et al.* (2024), Johnston *et al.* (2024) and Kelly *et al.* (2025). The development is now continued as **microparticlesAI** by **Hufnagl Chemometrics® GmbH** (<https://www.hufnagl-chemometrics.com>).

¹ ISO Search Engine: <https://www.iso.org/search.html>

- Dong *et al.* (2022) made a broad comparison of vibrational spectroscopy devices and softwares and asked the pointed question: “Are we measuring the same metrics?”. Concerning the state-of-the-art in ML and general data analysis approaches, there is certainly potential for further improvement. In that respect advanced AI/ML approaches are a promising technology to harmonise results and make studies more comparable.

Methods for Identification of Components

Raman Spectroscopy

As mentioned before, Raman spectroscopy is a non-destructive analytical technique that provides molecular-level information through the inelastic scattering of light. Its ability to generate distinct vibrational fingerprints makes it particularly suitable for the identification and characterisation of polymeric materials. In the context of MNP research, Raman spectroscopy has emerged as a valuable tool due to several advantages (Anger *et al.*, 2018; Araujo *et al.*, 2018; Cowger *et al.*, 2020):

- **Chemical specificity:** Raman spectroscopy provides detailed vibrational fingerprints that are highly specific to molecular structure. This enables precise identification of polymer types, even among chemically similar materials such as polyethylene (PE) and polypropylene (PP), which may be challenging with other techniques.
- **High spatial resolution:** Confocal Raman microscopy can resolve particles below 1 μm , while advanced techniques like Tip-Enhanced Raman Spectroscopy (TERS) (Shi *et al.*, 2017), Surface-Enhanced Raman spectroscopy (Xie *et al.*, 2023) or Raman tweezers (Gillibert *et al.*, 2019) extend detection capabilities into the nanoplastic range below 100 nm.
- **Minimal water interference:** Unlike FT-IR, Raman spectra are not significantly affected by water absorption, allowing direct analysis of wet samples or aqueous suspensions, an important advantage for aquatic microplastic studies (Nava *et al.*, 2021).
- **Compatibility with minimal sample preparation:** Raman analysis can often be performed directly on environmental samples (e.g., filters, sediments, tissues) without extensive chemical treatment or drying. This reduces the risk of altering or losing particles during preparation and supports high-throughput workflows.
- **Sensitivity to non-polar functional groups:** Raman is particularly effective for detecting non-polar polymers (e.g., PE, PP, PS), which may be less responsive in FT-IR due to weak dipole moment changes.
- **Wider spectral coverage:** Raman spectroscopy can access vibrational modes across a broader spectral range than FTIR, including low-frequency lattice modes and skeletal vibrations, which are useful for polymer differentiation.
- **Narrow spectral bands:** Raman spectra typically exhibit sharp, well-defined peaks, which facilitates resolution and accuracy in polymer identification, especially in complex mixtures.

These attributes are critical for analysing complex environmental matrices where plastic particles often coexist with organic and inorganic contaminants.

Despite its many advantages, Raman spectroscopy also presents several limitations that can hinder its effectiveness in MNP analysis. The technique is sensitive to fluorescence interference, which can obscure Raman signals, particularly in environmental samples containing organic matter or pigments. Acquisition times can be long, especially when high spatial resolution or

spectral quality is required, limiting throughput in large-scale studies. Additionally, Raman instruments are often expensive and require skilled operation, which may restrict accessibility in routine monitoring contexts. The interpretation of Raman spectra can be complex, particularly in heterogeneous mixtures or aged particles, where overlapping bands and low signal-to-noise ratios challenge manual analysis. These limitations underscore the need for complementary approaches, such as AI, to improve data processing and spectral interpretation, and support scalable, automated workflows.

AI/ML algorithms can automate spectral preprocessing steps including baseline correction, denoising, and peak extraction, thereby improving signal-to-noise ratio and overall data quality (Jin *et al.*, 2024). Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and one-dimensional CNNs (1D-CNNs) have demonstrated high accuracy (up to 97%) in classifying microplastic types directly from raw Raman spectra, reducing the need for extensive manual preprocessing (Qin *et al.*, 2024; W. Zhang *et al.*, 2023). Advanced Raman modalities such as spatial heterodyne Raman spectroscopy (SHRS) and stimulated Raman scattering (SRS), when combined with AI, enable rapid and high-resolution identification of nanoplastics in complex environmental matrices (Qian *et al.*, 2024). Additionally, AI-driven spectral matching and image reconstruction techniques have been used to enhance Raman imaging, allowing for improved detection of aged or irregularly shaped microplastics (F. Li *et al.*, 2024; Luo *et al.*, 2023). These approaches not only increase throughput and accuracy but also support quantitative analysis of microplastic concentrations in aquatic environments (Luo *et al.*, 2024). Overall, the integration of AI with Raman spectroscopy significantly advances the scalability, precision, and applicability of microplastic detection, particularly in real-world environmental samples.

Despite its transformative potential, the integration of AI into Raman spectroscopy for microplastic detection faces several critical challenges (Coca-Lopez *et al.*, 2025) related to spectral noise, complex and time-consuming preprocessing steps, limited availability of large, high-quality datasets, generalisation and domain shift, and the interpretability and transparency of AI models.

FTIR Spectroscopy

Fourier Transformed InfraRed (FTIR) spectroscopy is a technique measuring the interaction of IR radiation with a sample. The resulting interferogram is mathematically converted into a readable spectrum by a Fourier transformation. The type of output of the instrument depends mainly on the type of measurement that is performed and the type of detector that is used. FTIR can be split in two main categories: attenuated total reflectance (ATR)-FTIR or μ FTIR. ATR-FTIR uses a crystal as a contact point with the sample, where a IR beam is directed to the interface between the crystal and the sample. The energy absorbed by the sample is then measured and converted into a spectrum. In μ FTIR, the energy absorbed by the sample is calculated by measuring the difference between the incident and the transmitted IR light. The transmitted light can be detected by a Mercury-cadmium-Telluride (MCT) detector, which detects single point measurements, or a focal plane array (FPA) detector, which is capable of measuring thousands of spectra simultaneously. FTIR devices are typically equipped with a light microscope to visualize the sample and choose regions of interest for the measurement. The output data can thus be single-spectra data, a microscopy image combined with a spectra matrix linked by the measurement points position or a hyperspectral image.

The detection size range of ATR-FTIR goes from macroplastic (MaP) to particles down to approx. 300 μm but has recently been pushed down 1.3 μm using large area ATR-FTIR (Y. Liu *et al.*, 2024). The detection range of μFTIR typically spans between 300 and 20 μm (Chen *et al.*, 2020).

Even if proven as an efficient technique for MP identification, challenges remain to obtain an optimised data processing and analysis protocol. After acquisition, raw spectra are exported and need to be pre-processed to allow their correct later identification. Typical pre-processing involves the following steps (Renner *et al.*, 2019):

- Increase signal to noise ratio (smoothing)
- Perform baseline correction
- Selection of fingerprint regions
- Normalise data

The order in which the different steps should be applied to the raw data was suggested by Renner *et al.* (2019), who focused on MP detection. Yan (2025) recently suggested a new hierarchy-aware preprocessing framework for spectral data preprocessing for ML and quantitative analysis. The Table 1 presented in the referenced study provides a very complete list of the different methods available for each step, together with their advantages and disadvantages.

In the context of FTIR output data processing and analysis, AI could contribute to the following points:

- Context-aware algorithm for data pre-processing capable of dynamic adaptation to varying data conditions (Yan, 2025).
- Hybrid modelling framework that integrate physics based constraints to enhance robustness of data driven approaches (Yan, 2025).
- Reinforcement learning driven automation to optimize trade-off between computational efficiency and information fidelity (Yan, 2025).
- Non-specialist accessible tools.
- Integration of a variety of ML algorithms in an efficient and lightweight manner (Zhang *et al.*, 2022).

Mass spectrometry-based techniques

Mass spectrometry (MS) separates ionised components of samples based on their mass-to-charge ratio and identifies these through resulting mass spectra. Pyrolysis - gas chromatography – mass spectrometry (Py-GC-MS) is a commonly used MS technique for MNP research (Brits *et al.*, 2024; Dierkes *et al.*, 2019; P. Li *et al.*, 2023; Steinmetz *et al.*, 2022). Polymers are thermally decomposed into molecular fragments (pyrolysates) through pyrolysis, which are separated chromatographically and then identified with MS. Each chromatographic peak provides both retention time and mass spectral information, with peak area proportional to the pyrolysate mass. Characteristic pyrolysates serve as “fingerprints” for polymer identification, although chromatogram appearance depends on instrumental parameters (e.g., pyrolysis temperature, GC column conditions). In microplastics research, typically the method development requires polymer standards to identify characteristic pyrolysates of different polymer types (Okoffo & Thomas, 2024; Steinmetz *et al.*, 2020). Generally, proprietary software and spectral libraries are used. Some libraries (e.g. [F-search MPs 2.1](#)) classify chromatographic patterns and use these to identify polymer types, while others allow individual pyrolysate identification (e.g. NIST08

database), providing more control, but requiring expert analysis to identify characteristic fragments free from matrix or other polymer interferences (P. Li *et al.*, 2023; Z. Li *et al.*, 2022; Steinmetz *et al.*, 2020; Xu *et al.*, 2022). Data acquisition can be carried out in “full scan” mode, where full mass spectra for each chromatographic peak are obtained. Alternatively, “selected ion monitoring” (SIM) mode, targets characteristic marker ions of specific pyrolysates, increasing the resolution and selectivity. However, SIM mode requires extensive method development to identify these markers and ensure they are free from interference. Reproducing methods across laboratories is challenging, as retention times and fragment selection vary with instruments and pyrolysis conditions.

Other MS-based techniques have also been used for quantification of MPs. For example, TD-PTR-MS allows thermal desorption-based quantification and identification, TGA and TGA-FTIR provide thermal decomposition profiles (although not strictly MS techniques), MALDI-ToF MS gives information about polymer molecular weights and additives, ToF-SIMS characterizes surface chemistry, and ICP-MS quantifies metal additives.

The detection limits, in the case of Py-GC-MS, are dependent on polymer type and matrix, and have been reported in the range of 0.001 – 0.081 μg (P. Li *et al.*, 2023; Z. Li *et al.*, 2022; Steinmetz *et al.*, 2020). Other MS-based techniques have different detection limits based on the application.

There has been little previous work using AI to enhance the analysis of MPs using Py-GC-MS. Nijenhuis *et al.* (2025) used a non-targeted and multivariate approach for the improvement of the identification and quantification of MPs (PE, PVC, and PET) in human blood. Feature selection reduced quantification errors by up to 38 % (for PET). Matsui *et al.* (2020) developed an automated algorithm for the identification of plastics based on the generation of summated mass spectra for 11 different polymer types followed by comparison with a built-in library, allowing successfully identified in polymer mixtures. For the future, Jing *et al.* (2025) suggest that the application of AI could have the capability to select pyrolysates, apply peak deconvolution, address challenges such as environmental matrix interference and interference from other polymer types, as well as identification of indicator ions of individual pyrolysates to be used for qualitative identification or quantification in a recent perspective. Fingerprinting and clustering algorithms have also been applied to TD-PTR-MS and pyrolysis-MS datasets for nanoplastic detection in environmental samples (Forbes *et al.*, 2023; Materić *et al.*, 2020).

For Py-GC-MS, high-quality full-scan spectral datasets would be important for training ML models, as they capture the full range of pyrolysis products and potential interferences, ideally across different environmental matrices and many polymer types, including individual and mixtures. It should be possible for models to be implemented between different instrument conditions.

Discussion / Conclusion

Despite the urgent and widespread problem of microplastic pollution, standardized and broadly applicable characterization methods remain a major challenge. A single environmental sample can contain tens to hundreds of thousands of particles, generating large and complex datasets from spectroscopic, microscopic, or mass spectrometric analyses. Manual or semi-manual evaluation of such data is extremely labour-intensive and time-consuming, while also being prone to operator bias, thereby limiting reproducibility and comparability across studies.

AI and ML provide a promising pathway to address these limitations. By automating key steps such as data processing, particle detection, and polymer classification, AI can substantially reduce manual workload, increase throughput, and improve the reproducibility of results. Moreover, AI-based methods are capable of identifying hidden patterns in spectral or imaging data that conventional analyses may overlook, thereby opening new opportunities for understanding microplastic behaviour and impacts.

Within this context, microscopy remains one of the most widely used techniques for the detection and characterization of MPs. It fundamentally produces raw image data, digital micrographs or holograms. The integration of AI into optical microscopy aims to enhance accuracy, reproducibility, and scalability. Specific application areas include object detection, image classification, image segmentation, real-time particle detection, and shape or color-based classification, all of which significantly expand the analytical potential of microscopy-based microplastic studies.

To obtain information about the chemical composition of plastics, spectroscopic methods are widely employed, with Raman and FTIR spectroscopy being the two most common approaches. At present, analysis typically relies on spectral library searches following data acquisition. While effective in many cases, this approach can lack transparency and adaptability, and the processing of large datasets is often extremely time-consuming. Furthermore, spectra derived from heterogeneous mixtures or aged particles are frequently complex, with overlapping bands and low signal-to-noise ratios that complicate manual interpretation. These limitations underscore the need for complementary strategies, such as AI, which can improve data processing and spectral interpretation while supporting scalable and automated workflows. AI algorithms, for example, can automate preprocessing steps such as baseline correction, denoising, and peak extraction, thereby improving the signal-to-noise ratio and overall spectral quality.

MS represents another domain where AI has shown clear benefits. Applications include reducing quantification errors, improving peak deconvolution, and automating polymer identification from complex spectra, tasks that are otherwise labor-intensive and prone to variability.

Overall, current evidence demonstrates that AI offers strong solutions to longstanding analytical challenges in microplastics research, enabling more efficient, accurate, and reproducible workflows compared with traditional approaches. However, several barriers remain. One of them is the lack of large, diverse, and well-annotated datasets. Fragmented and inconsistent data often hinder model generalizability, with algorithms trained in one laboratory performing poorly when applied to environmental samples or to datasets generated using different pretreatment methods.

In conclusion, the complexity of the microplastics problem necessitates a multidisciplinary approach. Progress will depend on integrating the expertise of analytical chemistry and environmental science with the tools of data science. Future advances should focus not only on refining AI models but also on building the foundations for their effective applications. Such developments will enable robust, transparent, and globally coordinated efforts to address the microplastics crisis.

Literature and Knowledge Integration

While most AI contributions to MNP research target technical stages of the workflow, there is also a growing role for AI in *meta-level tasks*. These applications focus on how scientific knowledge is organised, synthesised, and made accessible. For researchers entering a rapidly expanding and fragmented field, AI can accelerate the discovery of relevant literature, highlight emerging themes, and reduce duplication of effort.

Key Challenges

- **Exploding volume of literature:** publications on microplastics have grown exponentially over the past decade, with tens of thousands of papers now indexed in bibliographic databases. Keeping track of protocols, validation studies, and analytical innovations is beyond manual capacity.
- **Fragmentation across disciplines:** MNP research is spread across environmental science, analytical chemistry, toxicology, and data science, with inconsistent terminology and metadata reporting.
- **Reproducibility and protocol comparability:** without systematic reviews or shared vocabularies, researchers risk reinventing workflows or missing relevant advances in other domains.
- **Barrier to entry:** early-career researchers and those new to the field often struggle to navigate the breadth of literature efficiently.

Current AI/ML Use

The list below includes mostly general uses, as these tools are largely independent of the disciplines:

- **Automated Literature Search and Summarisation**
 - Natural language processing (NLP) models can mine large corpora of publications, extract key terms, and generate concise summaries (Asmussen and Møller, 2019; Blanchy *et al.*, 2023; Schoene *et al.*, 2022)
 - Topic modelling (e.g., Latent Dirichlet Allocation, BERTopic) is being applied in environmental sciences to map research trends and thematic clusters (Asmussen and Møller, 2019; Laureate *et al.*, 2023).
- **Bibliometric Analysis and Trend Detection** (Verma *et al.*, 2022; Chen *et al.*, 2024)
 - Citation network analysis (using graph algorithms and community detection) highlights key authors, collaborations, and influential methods.
 - Term-frequency and co-occurrence mapping visualises how topics (e.g. “Raman spectroscopy,” “pollen interference,” “deep learning”) evolve over time.

- **Knowledge graph construction:** AI can link entities (polymers, analytical methods, sample types) across papers, creating structured databases for cross-querying. This supports interoperability and meta-analyses (Zhong *et al.*, 2023).

Roadmap

Beyond direct laboratory applications, AI has a transformative role in **knowledge integration**. By applying NLP, bibliometrics, and data mining to the rapidly growing body of MNP research, AI can help the community:

- Detect emerging trends early,
- Reduce redundancy,
- Build consensus on protocols,
- And accelerate interdisciplinary exchange.

Literature-mining and knowledge-integration tools can be thought as a **fourth pillar** of AI in MNP research, alongside sample collection, preparation, and analysis. Below are some examples of how this can be accomplished.

- **Interactive Literature dashboards:** develop web platforms that continuously scrape publication databases (via APIs like PubMed, CrossRef, or Dimensions), run NLP-based classification, and update word maps and citation networks for the MNP field.
- **Semantic search engines:** move beyond keyword search to context-aware semantic search. Researchers could query “enzymatic digestion of pollen interference in Raman analysis” and retrieve relevant articles even if phrasing differs.
- **Automated evidence synthesis:** use ML pipelines that not only summarise articles but also categorise them into evidence types (protocol, validation, case study, review), accelerating systematic reviews.
- **Cross-disciplinary ontology building:** AI can help build shared vocabularies across environmental, toxicological, and materials science studies, reducing ambiguity (e.g., “nanoplastics” definitions).
- **Open community datasets for bibliometrics:** establish shared, continuously updated datasets of publication metadata, openly available for researchers to train AI models that detect research gaps and harmonisation needs.

Here is a list of some available tools for researchers:

- **General bibliometrics & visualization:**
 - **VOSviewer** (free): create co-authorship, keyword, and citation maps. <https://www.vosviewer.com>
 - **CiteSpace** (free) visualise emerging trends and research fronts. <http://cluster.cis.drexel.edu/~cchen/citespace/>

- **Text mining and NLP frameworks:**
 - **BERTopic** (Python package): state-of-the-art topic modelling for large corpora.
<https://maartengr.github.io/BERTopic/>
 - **Voyant Tools** (browser-based, free): web interface for word frequency, term maps, and trends.
<https://voyant-tools.org/>
 - **NotebookML** (free and premium versions): Google's tool for content analysis with advanced options creating podcasts, videos and mindmaps.
<https://notebooklm.google/>
- **FAIR/open literature datasets:**
 - **Dimensions Free**: structured data on publications, funding, citations.
<https://www.dimensions.ai/products/free/>
 - **OpenAlex**: free open database of scholarly papers and metadata, ideal for automated mining.
<https://openalex.org>
- **Reference management with AI features:**
 - **Zotero** (free): includes plugins for automated PDF metadata extraction, citation networks, and integration with text-mining pipelines.
<https://www.zotero.org>

Conclusions

Artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) are no longer peripheral technologies in environmental research, they are becoming essential instruments for managing the scale, complexity, and interdisciplinarity of micro- and nanoplastics (MNP) studies. As shown throughout this roadmap, AI offers not only technical solutions for automation and pattern recognition but also a conceptual framework for turning vast, heterogeneous data into coherent scientific understanding.

Across the MNP workflow, **sample collection, preparation and analysis**, AI contributes by improving accuracy, reproducibility, and efficiency. In **sample collection**, robotic platforms guided by ML-based decision algorithms can enhance access to remote or hazardous sites, while adaptive sampling and sensor fusion enable dynamic survey designs optimised for representativeness. In **sample preparation**, where contamination, heterogeneity, and interference remain major obstacles, AI-driven quality control and feedback systems can introduce real-time optimisation and reproducible automation. These advances bring laboratory practices closer to the precision and traceability standards seen in other data-intensive scientific domains.

At the **analysis stage**, AI already plays a transformative role. Convolutional neural networks, transformers, and other advanced models are enabling automated particle detection, morphological classification, and spectral interpretation across optical, FTIR, Raman, and mass spectrometric techniques. The convergence of AI with imaging and spectroscopy supports high-throughput, standardised characterisation pipelines, substantially reducing human bias and manual workload. These developments promise to bridge the long-standing gap between experimental precision and large-scale environmental representativeness.

Beyond laboratory and field applications, AI also serves as a catalyst for **knowledge integration**. Natural language processing (NLP), topic modelling, and bibliometric analyses can now parse thousands of publications, mapping research trends, extracting metadata, and revealing conceptual linkages across disciplines. Knowledge graphs and semantic databases promise a future where analytical protocols, materials, and results can be interconnected through machine-readable relationships, fostering interoperability and enabling true meta-analysis.

However, this roadmap also reveals persistent challenges. The most significant are **data quality and standardisation**. AI models can only be as robust as the datasets on which they are trained; fragmented data, inconsistent metadata, and non-standardised reporting still limit generalisability. Collaboration between data scientists, analytical chemists, and environmental researchers is therefore vital to create shared datasets, harmonised ontologies, and open repositories that comply with FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles.

Future directions should emphasise **integration and transparency**:

- Developing **open and validated datasets** for MNP image and spectral analysis.
- Embedding **explainable AI** to improve interpretability and trust in automated decisions.
- Building **digital twins** and closed-loop systems for adaptive sample preparation and real-time contamination control.
- Expanding **cross-disciplinary platforms** that unite environmental science, toxicology, chemistry, and informatics within common AI frameworks.

Ultimately, AI and ML should not be viewed as end goals but as **enabling infrastructures** – tools that allow researchers to extract meaning from complex, multi-scale data while improving reproducibility and collaboration across laboratories. The integration of AI into the full MNP workflow will accelerate the transition from fragmented studies toward unified, quantitative, and predictive science.

As the community continues to refine both experimental and computational methodologies, the synergy between data-driven intelligence and environmental expertise will define the next decade of MNP research, turning complexity into coherence and data into actionable understanding.

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